

Cosmic star-formation history since $z \sim 5$ and faint radio populations

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Galaxy evolution across time, Paris, 2017

Motivation

Madau & Dickinson 2014

- SFR history weakly constrained after $z > 2$
- Unknown dust obscuration
- Need deep dust-unbiased data with good resolution
- What will future **radio** telescopes see?

Data

- VLA-COSMOS 3 GHz Large Project (Smolcic+17a)
- 400 hours, sensitivity: $2.3 \mu\text{Jy}/\text{beam}$, area: 2 sq.deg.
- COSMOS2015 optical/NIR catalog (Laigle+16)
- ~8000 radio sources with counterparts (Smolcic+17b)

credit: NRAO/AUI

Galaxy classification

- Radio luminosity vs. SFR from SED fits (Delvecchio+17)

- Radio excess $r = \log \left(\frac{L_{1.4 \text{ GHz}} [\text{W Hz}^{-1}]}{\text{SFR}_{\text{IR}} [\text{M}_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}]} \right) > 22 \times (1 + z)^{0.013}$

means at least **80%** of the radio emission is due to AGN

Luminosity functions

$0.1 < z < 0.4$, Med $z = 0.32$

$0.6 < z < 0.8$, Med $z = 0.695$

1.3 < z < 1.6, Med z = 1.44

$2 < z < 2.5$, Med $z = 2.2$

3.3 < z < 4.6, Med z = 3.69

4.6 < z < 5.7, Med z = 4.82

Star formation

Radio luminosity to SFR

- Radio traces IR which traces SFR
- IR-radio correlation $q_{\text{TIR}} \sim \log L_{\text{TIR}}/L_{\text{rad}}$, $q(z)$ from Delhaize+17

$$q_{\text{TIR}}(z) = (2.78 \pm 0.02) \times (1 + z)^{-0.14 \pm 0.01}$$

- Final conversion (using Kennicutt+98):

$$\frac{\text{SFR}}{M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}} = f_{\text{IMF}} \times 10^{-24} 10^{q_{\text{TIR}}(z)} \frac{L_{1.4 \text{ GHz}}}{\text{W Hz}^{-1}}$$

↑
smaller q = smaller SFR

Radio + UV

$\langle z \rangle = 3.7$

Cosmic SFR density history

Faint radio sky

Number counts

Number counts

Population fractions

Conclusions

- Radio as a SF tracer, need robust IR-radio calibration
- Possible underestimation of SFRD from UV at $z > 4$
- Below $10 \mu\text{Jy}$ at 1.4 GHz *everything* is a star-forming galaxy